

What's in a name: Understanding scientific names for our birds, according to the ICZN Code

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The Checklist of the Birds of New Zealand, published by the BirdsNZ Checklist Committee, represents the joint effort of generations of scientists working with birds in Aotearoa New Zealand. The list includes the scientific names for birds which have confirmed records here, as well as fossil records. It contains thousands of bibliographic references, tracking taxonomic shifts and nomenclatural changes. There are roughly 1100 scientific names currently in the Checklist, each of which conforms to the International Commission on Zoological Nomenclature's published Code, which mandates how scientific names are to be formed and changed.

At times, taxonomic revision may be necessary according to the Code. In order to see whether changes were necessary, I reviewed each name in the Checklist, looking at original descriptions, etymologies, and subsequent usages for each name. In this talk, I will cover some of the major reasons why dozens of names may need to be revised, focusing in particular on grammatical gender agreement according to Articles 30-34 of the Code, as well as First Revisers for certain names. I will discuss the process of changing the names, and why it is important to do so. Finally, I'll touch on issues with the Code itself and philosophical differences in its interpretation, with suggestions for how it could be improved in the ICZN's next edition.

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